

broadcast at 100 kg N/ha 35 d after seeding (DS) and at 50 kg N/ha 65 DS.

A second evaluation of folcystein in summer 1982 tested doses of 0, 200, 400, 600, and 800 ml/ha, applied at maximum tillering and at panicle initiation. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 4.5 m². Local recommended variety Culiacan A82 (135 d duration)

was seeded at 140 kg/ha. Nitrogen fertilization was the same as in the first trial.

In the first trial, the 400 ml dose increased yield the most (Table 1). Analysis of variance showed there were statistical differences between doses (D), and non-significant difference for timing of application (E) and the interaction D × E, for the second trial. The indication is that folcystein could be applied at any of the

two times. Three statistical groups were formed based on Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Table 2).

Although treatments 3, 2, 7, and 8 belong to the same group, in terms of yield and income after subtracting cost of the product and aerial application, the dose of 400 ml/ha at E₁ is the best choice, and is an effective yield stimulator. □

Environment and its influence

Seasonal influence and effect of growth regulators on rice spikelet sterility

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We studied the influence of seasons and growth regulators on spikelet sterility in rice *Oryza sativa* L. in field trials at CRR in 1977 rabi and kharif. Four modern rice varieties — Ratna, Pusa 2-21, Pallavi, and IET2233 — were grown in three replications in a split-plot design.

The following were applied as a foliar spray to the whole plant 3 d after anthesis: auxin H-61 (1:2000 concentration), 2,4-D (100 ppm), GA-3 (100 ppm), kinetin (100 ppm), and control (distilled water spray). The crop was grown under normal fertilization — 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. Irrigation and plant protection were

Effect of growth regulators on spikelet sterility of 4 rices, 1977, Cuttack, India.^a

Treatment	Sterility (%)							
	Ratna		Pusa 2-21		Pallavi		IET2233	
	K	R	K	R	K	R	K	R
Control	40.5	24.5	35.4	18.4	28.4	12.3	30.2	14.8
Auxin H-61	39.9	18.6	35.6	20.4	26.8	14.0	31.4	16.0
2,4-D	36.9	20.4	34.6	19.7	27.9	13.0	30.4	15.4
GA	41.5	24.6	36.2	19.7	29.1	13.1	31.8	15.3
Kinetin	26.3	16.7	26.4	16.8	20.9	10.4	25.4	12.7
Mean	37.4	21.7	34.2	19.0	26.9	12.9	30.0	15.1
			V	G	VG			
			K	R	K	R	K	R
SEM +			1.01	0.46	1.18	1.11	2.10	2.22
CD 5%			3.20	1.12	2.43	2.24	NS	4.49
CD 1%			5.88	1.71	3.28	3.00	NS	6.00

^aK = kharif (wet), R = rabi (dry), V = variety, G = growth regulators.

supplied when necessary.

Spikelet sterility was 92% higher in kharif than in rabi for the 4 varieties (see table). Ratna and Pusa 2-21 had higher sterility than IET2233 and Pallavi in both

seasons.

Kinetin significantly reduced spikelet sterility of all varieties in both seasons and was significantly superior to other growth regulators. □

Announcements

IRRI-Tanzania sign technical and scientific cooperation agreement

The Government of Tanzania and IRRI have signed a memorandum of understanding that calls for a 5-year program of scientific and technical cooperation.

The objective is to enhance Tanzania's capabilities for research on rice and rice-based cropping systems. Priority will be on genetic evaluation and utilization of

rice varieties appropriate to Tanzanian rice growing areas, development of improved rice-based farming systems to increase land use intensity and extend the rice growing area, training of Tanzanian scientists, and development and testing of appropriate machinery for small-scale farming.

Collaborative activities under the program will be based upon mutually agreed upon 2-year work plans to be developed

by the Tanzanian Ministry of Agriculture and IRRI. Research, training, and rice production programs are priority items in the initial work plan. □

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